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**STUDY ON NEXUS BETWEEN
MEDIA AND GOVERNMENT
ON
MEN SUICIDE
BY SPREADING DISINFORMATION
TO PROMOTE
TOXIC FEMINISM & MISANDRY**

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1 Synopsis:

Study on Men's mental Health & Suicide by Men covers a broad range of research on men's health and wellbeing. What causes men to die at such a young age? The primary Reasons for the most of the Male suicides are the daily abuse & harassment by women partners/wives using "women-centric" laws in India. Men suffer silently from mental trauma & other abuse from their spouse as they are told from their childhood that MEN do not cry & MEN do not show their emotions.

Women misuse these laws not to just settle the score, take revenge, but also to alienate their husbands/partners from their own Children, Parents and other immediate family members. Women file range of serious criminal cases such as Dowry Harassment (498A IPC), Domestic Violence, Dowry Prohibition and often Rape (IPC 376) and Unnatural Sex (IPC 377) including Maintenance case under Crpc 125 against the entire family of husbands / male partners. Such criminal cases not only destroy their career, livelihood and reputation in society but also destroy their and their families' lives.

The Supreme Court of India has called 498A IPC as "legal terrorism" which affect men's mental health. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but It is an effort to highlight the plight of men and also how main stream media spread misinformation and proliferate malafide propaganda to promote toxic feminism and misandry.

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2 Study Overview, Key Findings & Methodology

2.1 Introduction:

- In this article we the members of MyNation Hope Foundation would like to bring out the truth on Men's mental Health and Suicide by Men which is more than double of what above article and other main stream media publish. Most of the literature collected by NGO MyNation demonstrates that there is a dearth of research on men's mental health or overall health when someone is reported to be depressed due to marital distress or a stressful relationship. There is no government body or agency for men in distress to consult with, no funding earmarked to encourage any organization (governmental or non-governmental) to work for men's mental health issues or address their socio-economic problems or to support men in distress. All these above issues because of false information spread by Feminists & Women organizations which make ordinary public to think that there are more suicides among women rather than men.
- Worldwide around 800,000 people die due to suicide yearly, that's one person every 40 seconds. Of these 1,39,123 (18%) are residents of India. 70% of suicides are by men, and is mostly due to depression because of marital discord, which is responsible for their death. The overall male to female ratio of suicide victims for the year 2019 was about 70:30. This ratio was even worsen compared to year 2018 (68.5: 31.5). Globally, the suicide rate for

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men is twice than of women, that's 13.9 per 100,000 for men and 6.3 per 100,000 for women

- In India, the marital status of suicide victims is observed at 66.7% (92,757 out of 1,39,123) of the suicide victims were married, which shows there is a problem with their marriage and family. As per NCRB 2019 reports, there are two major causes of suicides i.e. 'Family Problems' and 'Illness'. They also reported that Family problems and related issues were behind 32.4 percent of suicides, marriage related problems (5.5%), 70.2 were male and 29.8 females for every 100 suicide deaths. The NCRB collects national-level data from various sources. Almost 68.4 per cent of male victims were married.
- However what is most shocking to learn that there is no Body (Government or NGO) be it NCRB, NHS, or Ministry of Health & Family Welfare record the exact reasons behind Male suicide. The exact reasons can be Domestic Violence, Abuse by their wives, and Threat of filing false cases or Female partner / wives using women centric laws to Legally Torture husbands / male partners to extort money and settle the score.
- Rather than grouping Male Suicide under family reasons; specific and detailed reasons should be recorded to understand why lakhs of MEN are committing suicide.

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- The problem is neither official Body (Government, Parliaments, Judiciary, and Police) nor other institutes (Media, NGO, Intellectuals) want to accept that MEN also do commit suicide due the torture, abuse and domestic violence by their wives / female partners

Suicide Victims by Sex and Age Group during 2019

- As per data provided by States/UTs.

2.2 Key Findings:

The majority of men feel shy to come forward to report abuse, harassment, misuse of law and so most men suffer in silence and die young. There are no support groups to help men. None of the study reports of suicide by men or details highlighting atrocities on men are acknowledged by any institute, government body, and the mainstream media is reluctant to publish abuse on men or health issues concerning men in particular. Recently there was report by British Broadcasting co-operation (BBC) namely “*What's behind suicides by thousands of Indian housewives?*” without mentioning any true statistics of Men

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suicides and only glorifying one third suicides of women just to promote vested interest of Feminists.

2.3 Methodology

Information for this report is sourced from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) various secondary sources, medical journals, and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics, etc.

3 Reality & Reasons behind MEN Suicide

3.1 Why are suicides so high amongst Indian men?

- The latest health statistics paints a grim picture of India's mental health of men revealing that one person commits suicide every four minutes. The National Health 2019 raises alarm over the increasing numbers of suicide deaths to 1,39,123 in a year.
- This makes it to 381 suicide deaths every day and 16 an hour.
- The data also show the increasing vulnerability of Indian men versus Indian women.
- Of the 1,39,123 people who killed themselves, 97,613 were men as against 41,510 women making it nearly 70.1 % of all the suicide deaths in India by men.

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- The number of suicides in 2000 by men has risen from 66,032 to 80,544 in 2008 and 97,613 currently. The number of male deaths from suicides is nearly double than that of females.

3.2 A Grim Situation - Government & Media's Deep Rooted Men Hatred Bias & Lack of Laws & Platform to protect them

- There is a deep rooted bias against MEN in the society. Government, Legislators, Judiciary, Police, Women NGOs / Ministries & Media always judge MEN with a misandrist & stereotype mindset
 - They believe MEN as oppressors and criminals
 - They also believe that Women Never Lie and Believe All Women
 - Women Words are gasped truth & God's commandments
 - Women Never commit crime and even if they then it is always fault of MEN
- In India there is a ministry of everything Women & Child Ministry, Women Commission, Transgender Commission & Even Animal Welfare Board. But there is No ministry or Commission for MEN. Where do MEN go or protest when they are abused by their wives or want to bring out MEN related health issues. And hence having no platform to voice out their problems they do silently suffer in the pain and take extreme step of committing suicide.
- India has enacted over 4 dozen+ Women Centric laws and they are often term as MEN slaughtering laws of India because of their biased nature. Be

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it Dowry Harassment (498A IPC), Dowry Prohibition (DP), Domestic Violence, Rape (IPC 376), Unnatural Sex (IPC 377), Maintenance laws (CrPc 125), POCSO, Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act (PoSH) & Many more. These MEN slaughtering laws are so draconian where

- Entire Family of husbands are dragged and thrown into jail based on Women testimony
- As per the laws MEN are routinely thrown to jail even they are not capable or able to pay maintenance thus turning innocent MEN into criminal. Various High Courts have also passed judgement where they explicitly mentioned MEN must beg, borrow or steal the money but pay the maintenance to their wives. India has becomes no MEN's land and banana republic where MEN are treated like 3rd class species.
- India is a signatory of UDHR (Universal Declaration of Human Rights) and under Article 11 of UDHR *"People are who are accused of crime are presumed to be innocent until proven Guilty"* Despite of India being signatory; It does not follow this natural law. Per contract India has enacted several laws where MEN (Yes special MEN) are presumed be guilty until proven innocent. To cite a few laws/examples
 - **Indian Evidence Act 114A:** *Where if a woman says she didn't have consensual sex with a Man; laws presume she did not consent for*

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sex or she was raped. Now burden of proof shifts to a Man where he has to prove that it was consensual sex

- ***Dowry Prohibition Act: DP Sec 8;*** *burden of proof shift to accused husband where he has to prove that he has not committed offence.*
- ***Domestic Violence Act Section 32:*** *Upon mere testimony of woman, court may conclude the offence & pass the order – Complete mockery of natural justice.*
- Indian Government bodies especially Women & Child Ministry (WCD) & National Commission for Women (NCW) are completely hostile towards MEN and they are enacted as such they want to teach the lesson to MEN for being their gender. statements made by head of above bodies & other ministers are not only sexist but misandrist; such examples are below
 - *Ms. Renuka Chowdhary (Ex – Women & Child Minister) – “**It is time for Men to suffer. You can not trust MEN or Husband**”*
 - *Ms. Maneka Gandhi (Ex – Women & Child Minister) – “**All Violence are Male Generated**”*
 - *Ms. Maneka Gandhi (Ex – Women & Child Minister) – “**MEN Never Commit suicide and never heard a single such case of male suicide**”*
 - *Ms. Anandi ben Patel (Ex. Chief Minister of Gujarat) – “**MEN are rejected maal**” (aka Men are rejected items)*
 - *Ms. Sagrika Ghosh (Journalist) – “**Indian Males as species are the Ugliest in the World**”*

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- Ms. Nandita Das (Actress) – **“Every Man is a potential Rapist”**
- *Not only that; Government’s hatred against even minor boys are shocking and disgusting. The Indian Government legislators (so called elected parliamentarians) are clapping and cheering on the news that Boys are lagging behind Girls in the Education.*

(Video clip can be seen here: <https://twitter.com/Gameof498A/status/1224146164137758720>)

Therefore it is clear that Systematic bias against Men, women centric laws and misandrist mindset of government, legislators, judiciary and media are among the biggest reasons where Men feel negated, unwanted gender in their own country & treated worse than Animals therefore forced to commit suicide

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4 Role of Media & Government and Their Narrative towards Men & Women

4.1 Media Bias: Always Taking Side to Women Gender Irrespective of the Facts

- Undoubtedly; Media always takes the side of Women and publish the narrative that suits to their feminist and misandrist agenda.
- Media often publishes one sided and incomplete facts which creates a perception among the society that no matter women are always on receiving side and always a victim. MEN can never be a victim and always a perpetrator.
- For example; BBC has published the story/article titled “What's behind suicides by thousands of Indian housewives?” (source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-59634393>) But never cared to publish to stories “What’s the reason behind suicides by thousands of Indian Married MEN? or Why are Indian Married MEN committing suicide 2.6x times than Married Women?”

Let us dive in to the BBC’s article titled “***Why do thousands of Indian housewives kill themselves every year?***” to further analyze it

- *According to the recently released data by the government's National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), 22,372 housewives took their own lives last year - that's an average of 61 suicides every day or one every 25 minutes.*

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- *Housewives accounted for 14.6% of the total 153,052 recorded suicides in India in 2020 and more than 50% of the total number of women who killed themselves.*
- *And last year was not an exception. Since 1997 when the NCRB started compiling suicide data based on occupation, more than 20,000 housewives have been killing themselves every year. In 2009, their numbers rose to 25,092.*

What's behind suicides by thousands of Indian housewives?

By Geeta Pandey
BBC News, Delhi

Why do thousands of Indian housewives kill themselves every year?

According to the recently released data by the government's National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), 22,372 housewives took their own lives last year - that's an average of 61 suicides every day or one every 25 minutes.

Housewives accounted for **14.6% of the total 153,052 recorded suicides** in India in 2020 and more than 50% of the total number of women who killed themselves.

- BBC report nowhere says there are 3 times more Men commit suicide in its news header but they spread disinformation in the name women which sells.

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- Both of these BBC and The Hindu reports contradicts its header with its news. The Hindu news says globally 1.2 million females are missing but in India its 46 million. Not sure learned Editors of The Hindu or other media studied in which school which teach them 1.2 million is greater than 46 million. If its 46 million in India alone then how come its 1.2 million Globally? Anyway this is how they want to sell their news highlighting with big statistics header in women name which sells like a hot cake.

4.2 Facts & Figures of MEN Suicides

- These are the reports and Statistics reported by BBC / The Hindu which is far from the Truth. There are many other main stream media published similar reports.
- Number of suicides in India 1971-2019, by gender, Published by Statista Research Department, Oct 11, 2021, and NCRB which shows more men are committing suicide more than women, but no main stream wants to talk about this burning issue? More than that no media even ready to publish this fact

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(All figures are in thousands) - Source: statistica 2019 & NCRB

- As reported by NCRB most of the suicide by Men is the result of marital discord. Here are some statistics of suicide for last 6 years which we have collected. None of these statistics are published by mainstream media which are controlled by feminists or anti-men.

YEAR	NUMBER OF MALE SUICIDE
2014	89129
2015	91528
2016	88997
2017	89019
2018	92114
2019	97613
2020	108532

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4.3 Lack of Research & Study on Violence against MEN

- There is a lack of literature on the systemic study of violence against men and the correlates to such domestic violence in society. A few small-scale studies have shown the rates of violence against men to be similar to that of women with a prevalence of psychological abuse and emotional violence of 32.8%. but no media report shows real statistics of men's suicide. Most of these reports and studies are sidelined by mainstream media and other organizations.
- These half-baked drafts are publicly supported and intensely lobbied by the feminist mafia and so become the law of the land in double quick time without delving deep into the possible consequences. Most of such acts and amendments are introduced very quickly without taking proper measures for society to adapt to the same. There are strong social prohibitions inhibiting men from being aggressive against women and harsh legal sanctions facing men who dare to transgress but rarely any social prohibitions or legal sanctions inhibiting women from being aggressive against men - that is the reason why it is often said that it's a crime being a Male or to be born as a Male Child.
- Some of the most compelling scientific evidence prove that women are no less violent than men. For more details please refer **CRIMES BY INDIAN**

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WOMEN – (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>). But it has been seen that women's groups have threatened and bullied researchers or media or law enforcement agencies even Judges by any means possible to stop them from presenting evidence of the tendencies of women to engage, as much as men, in the perpetration of domestic violence, and additionally to file false reports of sexual harassment, rape or abuse.

4.4 Government's Gynocentric Policies to Highlight Women Agenda at the cost of MEN's issues

- The government of India is over-enthusiastic to buy into the worldwide feminist ideology. But feminism disguised as women empowerment is causing severe damage to the unifying fabric of cultural, family, and spiritual values that defines this nation. The core mindset of the Government is misandrist which is visible in the lack of support and help offered to Men in distress. Men are left out in the cold with no Law to take recourse to when victimized and are therefore more commonly resorting to suicides. The rate of Men's suicide in India is alarming with male deaths from suicides being nearly double that of females thanks to rising numbers of fake cases, ill-treatment by society, and total neglect by the Government. (Ref: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4603151>)
- It's a shame to the government of India in front of Global community to show that there are more women are ending their life but they are silent

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on this media reports. No outrage from Ministry of Women and Child Development (**WCD**) / National Commission for Women (**NCW**) because all of these media reports they use to get Funds from Government and everyone knows, every minister has a cut to pay back as Party funds.

80% Funds for 'Beti Bachao Beti Padhao' Spent on Ads, Says Parl Committee

The central govt has spent 80% of the funds under the flagship scheme Beti Bachao Beti Padhao for media campaigns.

THE QUINT

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INDIA

2 min read

80% Funds for 'Beti Bachao Beti Padhao' Spent on Ads, Says Parliamentary Committee

- *"The Committee finds that out of a total of Rs 446.72 crore released during the period 2016- 2019, a whopping 78.91 percent was spent only on media advocacy."* said Parliamentary committee in Lok Sabha (Source : <https://www.thequint.com/news/india/beti-bachao-beti-padhao-80-funds-spent-on-ads-says-parliamentary-committee>)
- Government of India use billion on AD campaign to promote its vested interest which indirectly pay them back to its Party funds through main stream media. Who are the beneficiary of these AD campaign? Media

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houses. It's clear now as there is Nexus between Government of India, WCD/NCW and Media.

- Other than all above fake statistics / news than the Truth, here is yet another truth.

4.5 What it means to have more women than men in India

- Here is another media report on Sex ratio in India. *India has 1,020 females per 1,000 males, according to the latest round of National Family Health Survey (NFHS 2019-21). Mint delves into the data to understand the larger implications of such a skew towards women in the sex ratio.*
- *Caution is in order while reading the latest sex ratio number. India's projected population was 1.29 billion in 2016. If sex ratio were to be 991, as estimated by NFHS 2015-16, the population would then have comprised 643 million women and 649 million men. For a projected population of 1.36 billion in 2021, with a sex ratio of 1,020, there would be 688 million women and 675 million men. Such a break-up means a near-double rise in the population of women against that of men in the last five years (**45 million women vis-a-vis 26 million men**). The difference seems huge, even after factoring in differing death rates of the sexes. (Source : <https://www.livemint.com/politics/policy/the-implications-of-a-skewed-sex-ratio-for-india-11638122541930.html>)*

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- The most important question is to be asked to our Law makers / Politicians and other Ministers who promote their vested interests. If NFHS study shows there are 45 million women compare to 26 million men even after 46 million missing girl Child (The Hindu report) then how many boy children's killed at birth when there are more women than Men.
- As per Sex ratio, Population of Men reduced because there are more suicides and killed boy child at birth but no media ready to talk about it or publish it because they will not find any readers nor Government / Minister will support them to Publish their ADs on such media houses.
- In the year 2015-16 there were more men than Women but after the Promotion of #BetiBachao campaign (Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP) was launched by the Prime Minister on 22nd January, 2015) there are widespread atrocities on Men which is resulted in more suicides of men and killing of unborn male child resulted in imbalance in sex ratio.

5 Proof of Clear Nexus between Government & Media

There is a clear Nexus between Government and Media who constantly spread false propaganda against MEN to portray MEN as villain / animals and WOMEN as victim. This nexus can be proven clearly by following few real life cases / examples

5.1 Case 1: Delhi Road Rage: Jasleen Kaur vs Saravjeet Singh – 2015

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- There were some arguments between Ms. Jalseen kaur and Mr. Saravjeet Singh at the traffic signal of Delhi Road in year 2015
- To teach lesson and take a revenge against Saravjeet Singh; Ms. Jasleen kaur filed false molestation and sexual harassment case

Government Role to Encourage Women to file False Case and commit violence against MEN

- Without going into merit and judicial trial ; Gynocentric & Misandrist Politicians including Delhi Chief Minister – Mr. Kejriwal had applauded for brave act of Ms. Jasleen Kaur
- Delhi CM Kejriwal / DCP Delhi Police also awarded Rs. 50,000 for her bravery etc thereby establishing the fact that #BelieveAllWomen is sad reality in India and clear bias against MEN

Media's Role to destroy the life of innocent Man -> Saravjeet singh

- Many media channels including Times now (anchor : Aramb Goswami) ran a parallel Media Trial and called Mr. Saravjeet singh a Pervert, Delhi ka Darina (Delhi's Demon) etc
- Media had destroyed the Saravjeet singh life, reputation and self-respect

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- Even After fighting his case for many years ; when saravjeet singh was finally acquitted ; none of the media has apologized for tarnishing his reputation

There was No Repent/Apology and No Compensation from Judiciary or Government to Mr. Saravjeet singh

5.2 Case 2: Rohtak Sisters who have beaten 2 young Men in 2014/15

- 2 Sisters from Rohtak were waiting for the bus on their way home near Rohtak, Haryana. It was when two men from a nearby village approached and allegedly harassed them.
- 2 sisters who started beating those 2 MEN who were allegedly harassing them. Someone shot this video and it went viral.
- They have filed a case against these men under IPC 354 (assault of criminal force outraging women's modesty) and IPC 323 (voluntary causing hurt) and these 2 men were arrested

Role of Government & Media

- Many Politicians and Government (Chief Minister of Haryana) have praised these 2 girls for their brave act
- Chief Minister of Harayana Mr. Manohar lal Khattar announced the cash price of 31,000 Rs and nick named these girls as "brave hearts"

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- Whereas Media had portrayed these 2 men as villain and destroyed their lives and reputation
- Due to false cases and tarnishing the reputation of these 2 boys; they also lost the job opportunity in the Indian Army.
- After 40 witnesses these 2 men were finally acquitted in 2017 but the damage was done.

5.3 Media Bias to inflate its TRP at the Cost of Men's lives and reputation

- The role of media is highly biased against MEN cannot be ignored for sheer race for TRPs
- Media do not care or want to take responsibility of destroying innocent Men's lives, career and their reputation without verifying the facts of the case.
- Whenever a complaint is registered by woman; Media find it as Golden chance to inflate its TRP by blaming MEN; a typical stereotype mindset whereby they try to impose this false perception that MEN are always Criminal, Women are Always Victim , Women Never Lie & Believe All Women
- Media always give lecture to MEN that MEN should always respect Women, MEN should never hit back Women even Women hit MEN but never dare to preach vice-a-versa

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- Media know it very well that India being a Gynocentric country all laws are women centric and hence they get free pass even when they defame MEN on TV shows & debate programs
- However No Media would ever dare to question or defame a Women ; as they know very well that Government and Politicians would make it impossible for them to survive in this industry
- Government and its various ministries such as NCW/WCD Media spends crores of Rupees in advertising to media hence media has to appease government's pro women policies and women vote bank otherwise they might end up losing huge ad-revenue.

6 Conclusion

All above evidence & explanation leads to a conclusion that there is a clear nexus between Media and Politicians. If there isn't any Nexus questions arises as

- Why is government always silent when media publish a National Shame of Women suicides and missing Girl Child?
- Why is government not taking any action when Media openly defame MEN and calls them out Demon, Pervert & Rapist when they are accused by Women without convicted
- Why is government not setting up MEN's Commission to hear out their issues? And why isn't Media running widespread debate shows to

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highlight the dire need of such commission to put the pressure to government?

- Why Mainstream Media always publish the fake news, Statistics on violence against Women and but do not publish truth and highlight violence against MEN?
- Why do Media always publish one side narrative such as “What's behind suicides by thousands of Indian housewives?” And Why not “What's behind suicides by thousands of Indian men?”
- Why Government / legislators are cheering and clapping when boys are falling behind girls in education?
- How is it the moment of pride for Government when one gender is being systematically slaughtered with its gynocentric and misandrist policies and women centric bias laws?
- When Media is considered 4th Pillar of Democracy and having tremendous power to put the pressure to Government & its policy; why is it silently watching the systematic oppression & torture of MEN? Why is it not highlighting Men suicide and their issues?

7 Reference, Declaration & Disclaimer

7.1 Reference

- Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4431600>

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- STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH - EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON MEN'S HEALTH - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4603151>
- CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>
- MEN'S LIVES MATTERS - SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH // <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4649599>

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This Research study does not use any Fake statistics to justify any views expressed by the authors, Most Statistics used can be found on NCRB, respective Government Ministry websites or on medico legal Journals.